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INFLUENCE OF CRYSTALLIZATION CONDITIONS ON THE NANO-/MICRO-BEHAVIOR OF CARBON FIBER-REINFORCED PEEK COMPOSITE

CONTEXT

Thermoset Thermoplastic

ECONOMIC

Easier production of
complex parts at
higher rate

PERFORMANCE

Higher toughness

ENVIRONMENTAL

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ENVIRONMENTAL

PEEK/C fiber
(Unidirectional, 66 fiber wt. %)

$T_g \approx 143^\circ\text{C}$
 $T_m \approx 343^\circ\text{C}$

SEMI-CRYSTALLINE THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE: LIMITATION & QUESTIONS

Processing conditions

Performances of
thermoplastic composites

Transcrystallization (TC)

In the literature

- ✓ Influence of processing conditions (time and temperature) on TC ?
- ✓ Influence of TC on macro properties (σ_0 , E and K_{IC})?
- ✗ Impact of TC on mechanical behavior in the interfiber zones?

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CHARACTERIZATION OF SPHERULITES – Liq. N_2 fracture + SEM

→ Spherulites $\sim 1\mu\text{m}$ diameter

Spherulite nucleus Inter-spherulitic zone

CHARACTERIZATION OF TC – Liq. N_2 fracture + SEM

↳ Complicated in composite due to high V_{fiber}

CHARACTERIZATION OF SPHERULITES – POM

↳ Suitable technique for spherulites observation

$T_{isoth. crist.} = 200^{\circ}\text{C}$

$T_{isoth. crist.} = 300^{\circ}\text{C}$

CHARACTERIZATION OF TC – POM

↳ Complicated in composite due to high V_{fiber}

$$T_{isoth. crist.} = 315^{\circ}\text{C}$$

CHARACTERIZATION OF TC – POM

└───▶ Easier in model samples with few fibers

$T_{isoth. crist.} = 200^{\circ}C$

$T_{isoth. crist.} = 315^{\circ}C$

VARIATION OF THE LOCAL PEEK HARDNESS - NANOINDENTATION

↳ Hardness in intra-sph. zone and TC layer $\sim 50\%$ and 150% resp. higher than in inter-sph. zone (depth ~ 200 nm)

Nano Hardness

[MPa]

Indents at $\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$ from the fiber

VARIATION OF THE LOCAL PEEK YOUNG'S MODULUS - NANOINDENTATION

 E in TC layer \sim 70 % higher than in intra-sph. zone
 (depth \sim 200 nm)

 Indents at \sim 20 μ m from the fiber

TRANSVERSE COMPRESSION TESTS IN SEM + NANO-DIC

↳ Access to local strain field in the interfiber zones showing intense plastic localization

Mini compression machine

Unidirectional composite with nanometric speckle pattern
N. Klavzer, S. Gayot et al. (2023)

SEM imaging after each load increment

Micro-scale strain mapping from DIC

TAKE-HOME MESSAGES

Impact on mechanical behavior in the interfiber zones ?

TAKE-HOME MESSAGES

MICROSTRUCTURE

Liq. N_2 fracture + SEM

POM

Characterization of PEEK microstructure in composite more complicated than in the neat PEEK due to small interfiber distances ($\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$)

Characterization on model PEEK/C fiber samples

NANO- /MICRO- MECHANICS

Nanoindentation

H in intra-sph. zone and TC layer $\sim 50\%$ and 150% resp. higher than in inter-sph. zone

E in TC layer $\sim 70\%$ higher than in intra-sph. zone

Transverse compression in SEM + Nano-DIC

Access to μm -scale strain field in the interfiber zones

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Back-up slides

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](#)

Composites Part A

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/compositesa

Nanoscale digital image correlation at elementary fibre/matrix level in polymer-based composites

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Correlation Among Crystalline Morphology of PEEK, Interface Bond Strength, and In-Plane Mechanical Properties of Carbon/PEEK Composites

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Table I Summary of the Tensile Test Results and Crystallinity of Neat PEEK Resin

Property	Cooling Rate (°C/min)					
	1	80	160	600	1000	2000
	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD
Tensile strength (MPa)	108.5 \pm 5.0	93.8 \pm 9.0	92.5 \pm 3.5	71.7 \pm 10.4	57.5 \pm 3.5	53.8 \pm 3.3
Tensile modulus (GPa)	4.6 \pm 0.5	—	4.0 \pm 0.3	3.7 \pm 0.1	3.3 \pm 0.2	3.0 \pm 0.2
Failure strain (%)	3.0 \pm 1.4	9.8 \pm 1.4	7.9 \pm 3.0	—	115 \pm 7.1	183.3 \pm 5.8
Crystallinity (%)	38	30	28	26	19	17

MATERIALS

Semi-crystalline
thermoplastic

Unidirectional (UD)
composite

'Model'
samples

UD COMPOSITE

DEGREE OF CRYSTALLINITY - χ_c

DSC

'Standard conditions'

$\chi_c \sim 34\%$

$\chi_c \sim 36\%$

$\chi_c \sim 28\%$

'Amorphization'

$\chi_c \sim 15\%$

$\chi_c \sim 28\%$

$\chi_c \sim 18\%$

DEFECTS DETECTION – TOMOGRAPHY

PRINCIPLE OF NANOINDENTATION

Instrumented nanoindentation: *indentation depth* of the tip and the *force* are measured continuously during the test

Direct calculation of *Young modulus* and *hardness* from the “*force vs depth*” curve *

$$H = \frac{P_{max}}{A}$$
$$S = \beta \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} E_{eff} \sqrt{A}$$
$$\frac{1}{E_{eff}} = \frac{1 - \nu^2}{E} + \frac{1 - \nu_i^2}{E_i}$$

VARIATION OF THE LOCAL PEEK HARDNESS - NANOINDENTATION

TC layer

VARIATION OF THE LOCAL PEEK HARDNESS - NANOINDENTATION

Nano
hardness
[MPa]

NEAR FIBER MATRIX MECHANICAL PROPERTIES - NANOINDENTATION

NEAR FIBER MATRIX MECHANICAL PROPERTIES - NANOINDENTATION

CHARACTERIZATION OF SPHERULITES- AFM

Topographic contrast

Spherulite nucleus

SPHERULITES OBSERVATIONS - AFM

Topographic contrast
Etched samples

TRANSCRYSTALLIZATION OBSERVATIONS - AFM

Error image

- Difficulties:
- Differential erosion
 - Fiber/matrix interface decohesion during sample preparation
 - Presence of fibers => cutting line on the surface

TRANSCRYSTALLIZATION OBSERVATIONS - Liq. N_2 fracturing + SEM

'Model' samples

TRANSCRYSTALLIZATION OBSERVATIONS - POM

POM: polarized optical microscopy

Sample holder

Fibers

TRANSCRYSTALIZATION OBSERVATIONS - POM

'Model' samples

SPHERULITES OBSERVATIONS - STEM

SPHERULITES OBSERVATIONS - PERMANGANATIC ETCHING + SEM

M. Debaut (1990-1991)

Chemical etching step (5 min):
sulfuric acid, phosphoric acid, distilled
water & potassium permanganate

Rinsing step (1 min):
hydrogen peroxyde & water

Drying step:
Acetone

DEGREE OF CRYSTALLINITY – IMPACT OF COOLING RATE

DEGREE OF CRYSTALLINITY – IMPACT OF COOLING RATE

CRYSTALLISATION RATE – ISOTHERMAL CRYSTALLIZATION

IMPACT OF ELECTRON BEAM ON THE MATRIX - SEM

e- BEAM
→

SEM + DIC (TRANSVERSE COMPRESSION TEST)

4 kV, SE2, Pt coating

SEM + DIC (TRANSVERSE COMPRESSION TEST) N_{corr}

Type: exx-plot

Reference Name: Sample01StrainAnalysis090322_01.jpg

Current Name: Sample01StrainAnalysis090322_02.jpg

Analysis type: regular

RG-DIC Radius: 12 | Strain Radius: 5 | Subset Spacing: 5

Diffnorm Cutoff: 1e-06 | Iteration Cutoff: 50 | Threads: 4

Step Analysis: Disabled

RG-DIC Subset Truncation: Enabled | Strain Subset Truncati

Image Correspondences: [0 1]

Units/pixels: 0.0059069 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixels}$

Correlation Coefficient Cutoff: 1.5168

Radial Lens Distortion Coefficient: 0

Max: 0.0050 | Median: -0.0410 | Min: -0.1144

Type: exy-plot

Reference Name: Sample01StrainAnalysis090322_01.jpg

Current Name: Sample01StrainAnalysis090322_02.jpg

Analysis type: regular

RG-DIC Radius: 12 | Strain Radius: 5 | Subset Spacing: 5

Diffnorm Cutoff: 1e-06 | Iteration Cutoff: 50 | Threads: 4

Step Analysis: Disabled

RG-DIC Subset Truncation: Enabled | Strain Subset Truncati

Image Correspondences: [0 1]

Units/pixels: 0.0059069 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixels}$

Correlation Coefficient Cutoff: 1.5168

Radial Lens Distortion Coefficient: 0

Max: 0.0355 | Median: -0.0054 | Min: -0.0349

Type: eyy-plot

Reference Name: Sample01StrainAnalysis090322_01.jpg

Current Name: Sample01StrainAnalysis090322_02.jpg

Analysis type: regular

RG-DIC Radius: 12 | Strain Radius: 5 | Subset Spacing: 5

Diffnorm Cutoff: 1e-06 | Iteration Cutoff: 50 | Threads: 4

Step Analysis: Disabled

RG-DIC Subset Truncation: Enabled | Strain Subset Truncati

Image Correspondences: [0 1]

Units/pixels: 0.0059069 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixels}$

Correlation Coefficient Cutoff: 1.5168

Radial Lens Distortion Coefficient: 0

Max: 0.1171 | Median: 0.0181 | Min: -0.0121

IMPACT OF PROCESSING CONDITIONS - TRANSVERSE TENSILE TESTS

IMPACT OF PROCESSING CONDITIONS - TRANSVERSE COMPRESSION TESTS

